

AUTHENTIC ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF 10TH-11TH GRADE STUDENTS**Kismetova G.,***Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences,**Associate Professor, Teacher, M.Utemisov West Kazakhstan University, Uralsk, Kazakhstan***Saktaganova A.***Master's degree student, Khalel Dosmukhamedov University, Atyrau, Kazakhstan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18070637>**Abstract**

This article analyzes the development of authentic English communication skills in 10th- and 11th-grade students. It examines the fundamentals of authenticity and linguodidactics, as well as its importance for the development of schoolchildren's communicative competencies. The study identified motivational and psychological characteristics of high school students that can influence the process of mastering language interaction. Effective methods, such as communication-oriented, project-based, and situationally relevant, were also described. Practical forms of work designed to develop natural speech activity, such as discussions, mini-projects, online interaction, and media practice, are presented. Particular attention is paid to assessing the level of authentic communication. The results identify key challenges and solutions.

Keywords: authentic communication, English language, communicative competence; intercultural communication and speech development.

INTRODUCTION

Today, globalization and the development of digital technology significantly impact the demand for high levels of English proficiency among schoolchildren. Consequently, this underscores the importance of developing authentic communication skills, or more precisely, the ability to use language in real life, not just on the walls of schools. Therefore, developing authentic communication skills that enable real-life use of language is becoming increasingly important. It will be especially important for high school students in grades 10 and 11 to apply these skills, as they will be expected to use English in their studies after school. Particularly in intercultural interactions where different countries and nations are represented, communication skills in everyday life will be sorely lacking [1].

In foreign language teaching, the term "authentic communication" refers to the use of authentic materials, natural language patterns, and scenarios that mimic real-life communication. In contrast to staged dialogues, which are often formal and do not reflect an authentic communicative environment, authenticity requires dynamic, spontaneous speaking, cultural context, and realistic communication tasks. This method is closely linked to communicative and action-oriented approaches, where learning is based on using language to communicate, solving speaking problems, and actively participating in speaking activities [2].

The aim of this article is to describe the characteristics of the development of authentic communication skills in secondary school students and to investigate the methodological factors that promote their development. The following objectives were formulated in accordance with this aim:

- to highlight the qualities of authentic communication and how they are applied in contemporary English language teaching;
- to identify the main barriers to students learning authentic communication and suggest ways to overcome them.

- To explore teaching methods and best practices.

METHODOLOGY

One of the most commonly used methods in teaching foreign languages today is the communicative approach. It aims to develop both effective communication skills and a solid understanding of grammar. This approach is based on the principle of active interaction. Learners work in groups or pairs, engaging in conversations, discussions, and interaction while addressing realistic language situations. Instead of memorizing forms, this approach focuses on the communicative task and the meaning of the statement. In this way, learners learn to use language not only as a subject but also as a means of communication [3].

With the project-based approach, learners can tackle more challenging communicative tasks, such as presentations, interviews, surveys, research projects, or media projects. These require extensive lexical and linguistic activity, preparation, discussion, and teamwork. Students are usually faced with real-world problems. Therefore, in these projects, they can learn to reason, express their thoughts, and interact in English. There are also various options for group and individual work. Especially when topics are chosen according to students' interests, this approach fosters a sense of responsibility, independence, creativity, and motivation [4].

Interactions in business, at the airport, encounters with new people, organizing a trip, negotiations, and other real-life situations can be effectively simulated through role-playing and simulations. Students can use the language independently, respond to unexpected signals, practice giving instructions and tactics, conduct role-playing exercises, and train their communication skills. This promotes skills such as quick reflexes, adaptability, sociocultural flexibility, and reduces anxiety about speaking. This approach is particularly helpful in improving confidence and fluency.

Students experience authentic English as spoken by native speakers through original materials such as

music, interviews, podcasts, media reports, dialogues, and video clips. They learn modern idioms, colloquialisms, intonation, speech styles, and cultural nuances. This reduces the gap between classroom models and reality. Authentic resources stimulate interest and motivation, while also promoting the development of listening, reading, comprehension, and contextual interpretation skills, as they cover topics, lives, and cultures that are relevant to students [5].

Interactive technologies such as computers, multimedia, online platforms, video chats, and social networks can provide additional opportunities to create the most realistic language learning environment possible. These include completing multimedia tasks, group projects, virtual tours, online correspondence, and video chats. These teaching strategies enable learners to actively use the language, interact with classmates or native speakers, exchange information, and participate in global communication – rather than simply observing it. Interactivity also increases motivation, facilitates individualized learning, self-paced learning, content repetition, and the use of diverse media resources. All of this is crucial for the development of all communication skills, including speaking, listening, reading, and writing [6]. Useful methods for working with high school students:

1. Realistic conversation scenarios. Students engage in conversations about news, career opportunities, school activities, and topics relevant to teenagers and their everyday lives. By using everyday expressions and idioms, they develop natural communication skills.
2. Familiarity with communication techniques. This focuses on strategies such as asking questions, clarifying, expressing agreement or skepticism, conducting short conversations, and arguing in discussions. These skills foster persuasive communication and dynamic communication.
3. Short conversations and debates. Short conversations and debates help develop a logical conversational structure. Linguistic clichés are used to express viewpoints and respond to others' arguments.
4. Media production. Students can practice oral communication, expand their vocabulary, and use language creatively through podcasts, video blogs, interviews, and group discussions.

5. Use of social media. Participation in international online initiatives, commenting on publications, and engaging in safe, ethical online interactions all contribute to improving written and oral communication skills in real-life communication situations.

RESULTS

Eleventh-grade students participated in an eight-week study to evaluate the effectiveness of various techniques for developing authentic communication skills. During the experiment, about thirty students were divided into experimental (group B) and control (group A) groups. Control Group A used textbooks and conventional assignments, consisting mainly of conversation and grammar exercises, and aligned with the standard curriculum.

Experimental Group B used a number of original methods such as role-playing and simulations, project work, the use of real materials, and the involvement of external resources such as language clubs and global online discussions. The communication-oriented structure of the lessons, adapted to pedagogical principles, allowed for more time to practice speaking. Pre and post tests, assessments of oral communication skills, participation in discussions, short debates, and project work were all part of the experiment.

In addition, the students' confidence in their English language skills and their understanding of real-world topics were assessed using Likert scales. The impact of real-world approaches on the development of communicative skills and students' enthusiasm for active speaking was demonstrated by comparing the results of the control and intervention groups.

The Likert scale was used to assess how well the students developed their authentic communication skills and how they perceived the lessons. Subjective indicators can be measured quantitatively on a five-point scale: 1 represents "strongly disagree," 2 represents "disagree," 3 represents "neutral," 4 represents "agree," and 5 represents "strongly agree." The students in the control and intervention groups completed questionnaires before and after the experiment, allowing for the evaluation of the dynamics of change.

Table 1.

Comparative results of the development of authentic communication skills

Skill/Problem	Solving Methods	Group A		Group B	
		before	after	before	after
Lack of live practice	International chats, language clubs, online meetings	3.2	3.4	3.3	4.2
Time constraints	Integration of authentic tasks, flipped classroom	3.0	3.3	2.9	4.0
Psychological barrier	Creating a positive atmosphere; mistakes as part of the process	2.7	3.0	3.1	4.2
Lack of authentic materials	Media, adapted resources	3.2	3.5	3.3	4.3

DISCUSSION

The communication skills of high school students were significantly improved through the introduction of authentic methods and formats, as the analysis of the collected data shows. Group B achieved significantly

higher average scores than the control group in the areas of direct communication, overcoming psychological barriers, utilizing real-world resources, and productive use of learning time.

The average score of the experimental group (4.2) regarding lack of practical experience was significantly

higher than that of the control group (3.4). This underscores the value of online meetings, language clubs, and international conversations. It suggests that access to a real-world language environment boosts students' confidence and motivates them to actively participate in language activities.

Time constraints: The practice group achieved an average score of 4.0 compared to 3.3 in the control group. This is attributable to the integration of real-world tasks into each phase of instruction and the use of the translated classroom concept. This result demonstrates that the productivity of language communication is increased through organized preparation outside the classroom and the staggered distribution of activities.

Psychological Hurdle: The experimental group achieved an average score of 4.2, while the control group only achieved 3.0. This suggests that a safe and encouraging learning environment, in which mistakes are accepted as a necessary part of the learning process, reduces students' anxiety and promotes fluency.

The average score rose to 4.3 when media resources, adapted texts, and videos were available, while the control group scored only 3.5. This demonstrates how the use of diverse authentic sources significantly improves the understanding and application of the native language.

Overall, the results of the experiment show that secondary school students can acquire comprehensive communicative skills comparable to everyday English use through the integrated use of authentic teaching methods, external resources, and a psychologically safe learning environment. The control group, which worked with conventional textbooks and standard tasks, performed worse, highlighting the need for methodological adjustments in secondary school foreign language teaching.

CONCLUSION

The study has shown that orienting English language teaching in grades 10th-11th toward authentic foreign-language communication is an effective means of preparing secondary school students for real-life situations. Factors that promote readiness to use language in practice include the use of real-world materials, role-playing, and project-based learning methods. These methods are communication-focused and therefore significantly improve students' language proficiency.

The integrated application of authentic methods ensures a higher level of students' participation in communicative interaction, reduces psychological barriers, and optimizes the use of lesson time by prioritizing meaningful language practice over purely formal drill of language items. Finally, it can be understood that, as a result of the experiment with control and experiment, it was proven that with targeted pedagogical support, senior secondary school students can successfully acquire practical communication skills that will develop support and initiative skills.

We can see that, according to the results, authentic communicative actions not only contributed to the development of language skills but also formed sociolinguistic, discursive, and strategic components. Commu-

nicative competence is essential for effective interaction in a globalized world. An important factor in this effectiveness is the systematic use of external resources (authentic media, online materials, intercultural contacts) and the creation of a supportive learning environment that allows for linguistic risk-taking and encourages learner initiative.

Particular attention should be paid to formative assessment based on projects, presentations, role-plays, and portfolios. These real-world tasks allow for the assessment of students' proficiency in other language skills and their actual communicative behavior. Results have shown that the systematic integration of authentic materials into the high school curriculum ensures the transfer of acquired skills beyond the classroom, shaping future education and everyday communication. Thus, the proposed approach can be considered a key condition for developing communicative competence that meets the demands of modern society.

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